

Enhancing Emergency Response Efficiency: A Geospatial Machine Learning Approach to Predicting False Fire Alarms in the West Midlands

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Summary

This study proposes a predictive framework for identifying false alarms for Fire and Rescue Services using geospatial machine learning. False alarms refer to emergency alarms where no actual emergency exists. In 2023, they accounted for 40.7% of annual fire service incidents in England. False alarms cause significant drain on public resources and compromise fire service readiness for real incidents. To address the challenge of false alarms, we developed an XGBoost model to predict whether an incoming call-out is a false alarm. Based on spatio-temporal features of historical incidents in the West Midlands, the model achieved an accuracy of 86.7%, with only 1.7% chance to misjudge real incidents as false alarms. Further, if fire services implement this tool and suspend responding to the predicted false alarms, they would save Mobilisation-to-Arrival Time by 20.96%, which significantly improves operational preparedness. This research demonstrates the value of geospatial machine learning in transforming emergency service operations.

KEYWORDS: False alarm prediction, Fire and Rescue Service, XGBoost, Geospatial Intelligence, GIS.

1 Introduction

Ensuring quick response is the core of protecting life and property from fire. However, the efficiency of the Fire and Rescue Service (FRS) is increasingly undermined by the prevalence of False Alarms (FAs). FAs refer to emergency alarms where no actual fire or non-fire incident exists. In 2023, FAs constituted 40.7% of all FRS incidents in England (Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government, 2025), which incurred an estimated economic and social cost of £34.9 million (Jack Pickering et al., 2023). Beyond the financial burden, FAs also increase response times for Real Incidents (RIs) by occupying available fire engines. Therefore, reducing unnecessary dispatches caused by FAs is crucial for improving fire service efficiency and saving public resources.

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While remote sensing and GIS have been frequently used to monitor wildfires (Di Giuseppe et al., 2025; Wooster et al., 2012) or improve indoor fire detection (Mseddi et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2019), there is a lack of geospatial research regarding the spatio-temporal patterns of FAs. This study fills this gap by applying a geospatial machine learning approach to predict whether an incoming call-out is a FA, thereby supporting smart operations in fire service.

Figure 1: Fire stations and false alarm density in the West Midlands (EPSG:27700).

2 Data and Case Study

The study focuses on the West Midlands Combined Authority, a metropolitan region of 902 km² with a population of over 2.9 million (Figure 1). Two primary datasets from May 2021 to April 2024 were utilised. First, the incident dataset contains 79,775 records with attributes of time, location, and incident type, and was used to train machine learning models for false alarm prediction. Second, the fire engine mobilisation dataset contains detailed logs of fire engine movements and was used to estimate potential time savings from false alarm prediction.

Two additional geospatial layers of land use and deprivation were integrated. Land use data from OpenStreetMap (2025) were used to capture the built environment's influence on alarm frequency and it contains 48 categories such as commercial, education, and industrial areas. The English indices of deprivation 2019 (IMD 2019) (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2019) at the Lower Super Output Area (LSOA) level were integrated to account for the correlation between urban deprivation and incident patterns.

3 Methodology and Results

3.1 Model Development

XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting), a supervised learning model, was employed to classify incidents as either a RI (0) or a FA (1). Given the severe consequence of misclassifying an actual fire, the model was trained to balance the overall accuracy and the False Positive Rate (FPR), which is the possibility of misclassifying RIs as FAs. The FPR is defined as:

$$FPR = \frac{FP}{FP + TN} \quad (1)$$

Here, FP (False Positive) represents the number of RIs that are incorrectly predicted as FAs, and TN (True Negative) represents the number of RIs that are correctly identified.

Figure 2: Model performance: (a) confusion matrix (FA = false alarm, RI = real incident) and (b) ROC curve.

3.2 Performance and Impact

The model achieved an accuracy of 86.7% with a FPR of 1.7% (Figure 2). This means that 86.7% of total incidents were correctly classified and only 1.7% of RIs (176 out of 10,232) were falsely classified as FAs.

We estimated the potential savings from this false alarm prediction in a scenario where fire services do not respond to predicted false alarms. Mobilisation-to-Arrival Time (MAT) is defined as the interval between the initial station alert and the arrival of the first responding engine at the scene. Results indicate an annual saving of 876.8 hours in the West Midlands, which represents a 20.96%

reduction in MAT. At the station level, the proportion of MAT savings from FAs ranges from 7% to 34% (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Annual MAT (Mobilisation-to-Arrival Time) and the MAT for predicted FAs by fire station.

4 Conclusion

This research proposes a data-driven approach to support fire service operators by predicting incoming false alarms. The deployed XGBoost model achieved an overall accuracy of 86.7% with only 1.7% real incidents misclassified as false alarms. In the future, the model will be tested with new policies of fire service response, such as stopping response to automatic fire alarms in commercial buildings in working hours (London Fire Brigade, 2024). With more tests under real-world settings, the proposed model is expected to support fire service with smarter decision making strategies.

5 Biography

Shitian Zhang is a PhD candidate at the Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA), University College London. His research focuses on agent-based modelling and the optimisation of public emergency services using GeoAI.

Huanfa Chen is an Associate Professor in Spatial Data Science, at the Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA), University College London. His research draws on GIScience, machine learning, and spatial optimisation to address contemporary challenges in the planning and operations of urban services, incl. policing, fire services, public health, and transport.

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